

CASE STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF COVID 19 ON MANAGERIAL COMMUNICATION IN ROMANIAN SMEs

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Abstract

Purpose - To analyse the communication strategy in terms of effectiveness and efficiency, for the company and for the health and safety of employees, and the reintegration into the workplace of people who worked during the pandemic in a telework or hybrid system in an SME in Romania, which had NON-EU employees.

Methodology/approach - Bibliographic study method - due to the multitude of information that is constantly exploding, this method is vital to any research study. The case study method - is a suitable method if a full and in-depth investigation of a topic is desired.

Findings - Remote and work from home have become the new normal, post-pandemic. Communicating with employees has become a top priority for businesses.

Research limitations/implications - The limitations of the research are due to the fact that this research was conducted on a single SME.

Practical implications - It consisted of a case study carried out on a communication plan at an SME in Romania.

Originality/value - It is valued by the case study analysis and conclusions.

Key words: Influencing managerial communication in pandemic and post pandemic period, Managerial communication during pandemic, Managerial communication strategy in post pandemic period.

Specific aspects of communication during the COVID 19 pandemic reflected in specialized literature

Communication is an art that extends beyond words. Even if there is no unanimously accepted definition among communication experts, it essentially offers the establishment of relationships between people, no matter in what form it is used. Managerial communication is a key factor in any business and is needed both internally and externally. The realities of the pandemic, and later the post-pandemic period, have brought to the surface major challenges for even the top managers and entrepreneurs. With the emergence of the SARS-COV2 COVID-19 virus, the world has faced situations not seen in the last century. Both the public and private systems had to reconsider their activities, especially human resource management, because of the health protection rules that emerged immediately after the virus emerged.

The communication plans had to be revised because of the recommendations given by the WHO and especially because people's health was at risk.

In 2020, Mala (2020) started to draw managers' attention to issues that will affect small and medium-sized enterprises in particular, namely: 1. Financial security and job protection, 2. Employee health, safety and well-being, 3. Transition and management of work from home, 4. Frequent and clear communication with employees to keep them up to date with changes.

Joel Carnevale (2020) pointed out that the pandemic has had a big psychological impact on employees, with uncertainty at every turn. At the same time, the author also pointed out that more attention should be paid to workplace stress and working conditions, as employees are the viable face of any business.

Lewis (2020) pointed out that during the pandemic period, both employees and especially managers wanted to rethink health policies so that employees could be given the opportunity to seek medical attention in case of symptoms or illnesses, to avoid hospitals and incur the related costs.

Marwitz (2020) offered seven best practices in managing employees during the pandemic, including 1. Continuous communication, 2. Continuous verification of legal provisions, 3. Successful planning for remote work, 4. Consider the possibility of employee illness or quarantine, 5. Consider when employees are affected by school closures.

Singh (2020) suggested a number of strategies for managers, namely: 1. Companies that had vacancies needed to consider the new rules in labour law, and also in health rules legislation, 2. Post pandemic, managers need to pay more attention to employees' health and well-being, creating employer-employee relationships is a must, 3. Employers need to pay attention to digital literacy and the possibility to quickly organise work at home in case of a new pandemic etc.

In 2021, based on an analysis, the author showed that 60% of employees believe that the company will prioritize continuity over job security (Drosky, 2021), the same analysis showed that 44% of managers had the same opinion.

Case study - Analysis of changes in communication in an SME in Romania

While carrying out the case study on the communication plan of a small enterprise, whose activity is the wholesale of ceramic, glassware and maintenance products, we found a quite significant fluctuation of employees from the beginning of the pandemic to its end.

Figure 1

Before the pandemic started, the communication plan was hierarchically structured, with information/reports being passed on verbally and only those in management communicating the information in writing. The communication plan was simple, but the information was prone to being lost or misunderstood.

At the beginning of the pandemic, the case study company had 14 employees in various positions, both executive and managerial, all Romanian citizens. In 2021, the company employed 78 non-UE citizens from Nepal. At the end of the pandemic period, i.e. in March 2022, the company still had 3 employees, of which 2 were non-EU citizens.

As a company, which had to execute its part of the contracts, i.e. existing orders, it was impossible to work from home. Packaging, i.e. packing products for delivery, is a process that includes thousands of materials such as cardboard, polystyrene, thermo foil, etc., and some parts of the process include the use of certain equipment. Given the above mentioned aspects, the company adopted since the beginning of the emergency a hybrid work system, whereby employees were physically present at the workplace 2 days/week, which was decided on the basis of an assessment of risks to the health and safety of employees.

In order to streamline the work of people at home and people physically at work, a somewhat standardised communication plan was adopted, with procedures and a matrix of responsibilities. The responsibility matrices were reconsidered and adapted to work from home, excluding responsibilities for physical verification or travel. Each activity in the responsibility matrix has a standard procedure that specifically explains the activity to be performed, how much time is allocated to the activity and to whom the activity should be reported. This model involved hierarchical communication, with each employee reporting the work performed and any problems encountered to the direct supervisor.

The communication had to be in writing, so that it could be followed up by the company's management. In order to monitor the effectiveness of this communication plan, the company required an Ishikawa analysis to be carried out to analyse the problems, then a SWOT analysis was used. At the end of each month, the company's management met via an online platform to review the reports made by each line manager.

The final monthly report was finalised by the company's administrator based on the analysis and conversations with the line managers. Based on these reports the administrator proposed changes to the communication plan. Also any form of communication that included human interaction was limited, in the sense that any document requesting something from the administration or management was transferred to standardized and typed documents. These documents were made available by the company, and through which the aim was to reduce human interaction as much as possible.

In 2021 when the company received the foreign employees, the communication system was changed, because the new employees were in manual packer positions, making it impossible to work from home. Prior to the arrival of the employees, another risk assessment was carried out, suggesting normal working hours, but with more frequent hourly breaks so that the premises could be ventilated. The whole communication plan was also rethought so that new employees could understand it. All responsibility and procedure matrices have been translated into English. After their arrival, the company was faced with a problem not taken into account, namely the low level of understanding of English. The documents were re-translated into Nepalese so that the instructions could be understood much better.

Once the problem of communicating how the work would be carried out was solved, the company encountered problems with understanding the prohibitions imposed at the time by the Romanian state, and with understanding the labour legislation in terms of their rights and obligations. As the cultural differences were major, in the first months after the employment of foreign citizens, the company faced various problems such as unjustified absence from work, leaving the workplace for longer periods of time without breaks, etc.

In order to solve the problems of understanding the legislative rules, explanatory posters, both with written message and illustrations, were made to be more easily understood in both English and Nepali. Explanatory classes were also used to explain the labour legislation to non-ueue people to eliminate this problem as well.

After the end of the alert period in March, the company reconsidered the communication plan, and all the employees' work. The administrator decided that some areas of activity should remain in a hybrid system, namely accounting and people in charge of online sales platforms. From the communication plan adopted during the pandemic period, the aspects of standardised communication via matrices and procedures, written reporting via emails and weekly reviews were kept.

To reintegrate people into the workplace, especially those who worked in hybrid, a temporary communication plan was adopted, which involved the HR person spending 2 hours per week physically talking to employees to establish their needs. This temporary plan was adopted for a period of one month. All aspects of the communication plan that included the standardised process were retained by

the company and were considered by them to be the most effective aspect of the communication plan during the pandemic.

Conclusions

In our opinion, the temporary communication plan was an important factor because the standardized, though efficient, process is rigid, with human interaction taking place only via email. Interpersonal communication is the most important factor for creating relationships between people, due to the fact that it involves both verbal and nonverbal communication, which have a greater psychological impact, than communication via email.

Interpersonal relationships, especially at professional level, are based on communication. Both between colleagues and between managers and employees, relationships can be established when there is communication.

In conclusion, the company's communication plan has been drawn up responsibly, in the sense that it has been developed on the basis of recommendations, and on the basis of a risk assessment. The plan was executed by both manager and employees, which indirectly led to teamwork. The standardisation of communication during the pandemic period was effective for the whole company and subsequently one of the most appreciated aspects by employees and management. In my opinion the communication plan also had some gaps and omissions, such as not addressing the situation where employees would get sick or the situation where they would be affected by school closures. We consider it a positive aspect that standardised communication, and some aspects of the communication plan, were maintained in relation to home working. Practice has also shown that regardless of culture, people can be made more effective if there is a well-done and executed communication plan.

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